

ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH HIGH RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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1 Abstract

During the last decade, Computed Tomography (CT) has progressed to higher resolution and faster reconstruction of the 3D-volume. Most recently it even allows a three-dimensional look into the inside of materials with submicron resolution. High-resolution X-ray CT allows the 3D visualization and failure analysis of the internal microstructure of textile and composite materials – even where 2D X-ray microscopy would give only the integral information of the overlaying bundles of fibers. By means of nanofocus tube technology, nanoCT[®]-systems are pushing forward into application fields that were exclusive to expensive synchrotron techniques. But their potential, convenience and economy of these lab systems is often underestimated.

2 Method

Especially for modern composite materials which are used in very expensive or safety relevant applications, CT is ideal to accompany the product from development to final quality control. The tube based CT measurements for the study were performed with a granite-based phoenix|x-ray nanotom[®] s and m CT systems (GE Measurement & Control Solutions, Wunstorf, Germany, fig. 1) equipped with a 180 kV / 15 W high-power nanofocus tube with Tungsten or Molybdenum-Targets. The tube offers a wide range of applications from scanning low absorbing samples in nanofocus mode with min. voxel sizes <300 nm and high absorbing objects in high power mode with focal

spot and voxel sizes of a few microns. The nanotom is the first 180 kV nanofocus computed tomography system which is tailored specifically to high resolution applications in the field of material science and micro electronics. Therefore it is particularly suitable for nanoCT-examinations e.g. of synthetic and composite materials, metals and metal foams, ceramics etc.

Fig 1: With its small footprint, GE's phoenix nanotom is uniquely suited for laboratory applications.

The CT volume data set can be displayed in various ways; it can be sectioned and sliced in all directions, rotated and viewed from any desired angle. Highly applicable to a variety of fields, nanoCT can be a viable substitute for destructive mechanical slicing and cutting. Differences in material, density or porosity within a sample causing a contrast in

absorption can be visualized and data such as distances can be measured. Some of the many applications of nanoCT include the analysis of fiber textures, air inclusions or cracks in composite materials with voxel resolutions down to less than one micrometer. Since the contrast can be as low as 0.2 % it allows even a segmentation of e.g. C-fibers in a C-based matrix (Fig.2).

Fig. 2: nanoCT of carbon fibres and pores in polymer matrix scanned with a phoenix nanotom with molybdenum target with 0.5 μm voxelsize. Diameter of single fibres is ca. 1-5 μm . The texture of the fibres is clearly visible.

Fig. 3: Sieve scanned with 4 μm voxelsize. Diameter of the small fibers is 0.012 mm, of the large fibers 0.5 mm. Courtesy by RWTH Aachen, Institut für Textiltechnik, Germany

3 Results

The CT results obtained with the nanotom allow analyzing the spatial microstructure of the sample with submicrometer resolution: Any internal detail that corresponds to a contrast in material, density or porosity can be visualized and quantities like

distances can be measured. Components of a sample may be visualized individually by suppressing the contrast of all but the material of interest. By this way, also normally hidden pore networks may be analyzed.

Fig. 3: nanoCT of a glass fiber reinforced plastic. Clearly visible is the orientation and distribution of the 10 μm thin fibers as well as accumulations of the mineral filling material. The plastic is blinded out.

Fig. 4 a+b: nanoCT of an induction welded joint of an aluminum plate (corundum blasted) with carbon fibers in polyamide matrix. The voxel size of the scan is $0.7 \mu\text{m}$. Clearly visible is the orientation of the fibers ($7 \mu\text{m}$ thick), delaminations between the fiber bundles (1) as well as air entrapments (2) in the welding zone uncovering not optimized manufacturing parameters. Bright points in the aluminum plate indicate small particle inclusions with higher X-ray absorption. The length of the edge of the 3D visualisation (left image) is about 1 mm.

Fig. 5: nanoCT of a polymeric alloy (PP + talcum) scanned with a molybdenum target at $0,4 \mu\text{m}$ resolution. Bright contrast characterizes higher absorbing particles in the virtual slice. Measured particle size: $0,938 \mu\text{m}$. Courtesy of FH OÖ Wels.

Fig. 6: Stitched CFRP. CT Volume data with $3 \mu\text{m}$ voxelsize. The diameter and orientation of fibres can be analyzed, the measured fiber diameter is $7\text{-}14 \mu\text{m}$. Additionally, the orientation of the stitch yarn can be analyzed. Courtesy of RWTH Aachen, Institut für Textiltechnik, Germany.

4 Conclusion

Open tube based laboratory X-ray systems with spatial resolution of down to $< 1\mu\text{m}$ are commercially available. The contrast of state of the art systems can be as low as 0.2% allowing a segmentation of e.g. C-fibers in a C-based matrix. High resolution CT offers a complete 3D imaging of the specimen allowing among others:

- Virtual cross-sectioning in arbitrary direction to complement or substitute classical cross-sectioning microscopy techniques

– Failure analysis of e.g. cracks, delamination, voiding...

– Quantitative data analysis like: fiber orientation, void analysis, particle size analysis, wall thickness analysis, extraction of polygon meshes for simulation